

MACROETHICAL DEVELOPMENT IN CIVIL AND ARCHITECTURAL ENGINEERING EDUCATION

(SHORT)

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ABSTRACT

This short research paper presents the early stage of an ongoing project in engineering ethics education. Given the impact of civil and architectural engineering and the profession's obligation to uphold public welfare and trust, students must understand macroethics, engineering's responsibilities to the human, natural, and built environment. The Bachelor's curriculum plays a key role in developing ethical responsibility, as a site of professional socialization and the only institutionalized training most engineers receive. Students are also exposed to ethics, values, and the societal impacts of engineering via informal learning before and during their university experience. The present project is designed to explore how civil and architectural engineering students make meaning of their societal responsibilities by examining their conceptualisation of the impact of engineering and the factors that influenced it. This study employs a constructivist grounded theory (CGT) approach and draws on interviews with Bachelor's civil and architectural engineering students in Belgium and the United Kingdom. Data collection and analysis are ongoing simultaneously with the aim of generating a novel theoretical model of macroethical development. This short paper introduces the theoretical and methodological approach of the study, anticipated outcomes, and next steps.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Engineering Ethics Education

In charting the future of engineering education, Sheppard and colleagues point out that “engineering inevitably means intervening in the world,” and therefore “all engineering projects carry with them responsibility for the effects of those interventions” [1] (p. 9). They call for powerful learning opportunities, so engineers understand “that social and ethical connections are as important, if not more so, as electrical and mechanical ones” (p. 9). However, the integration of ethics in engineering education has lagged behind recognition of its necessity by both industry professionals (e.g., [2]) and accreditation bodies (e.g., [3]). An understanding of the process through which students develop their professional and societal responsibility can inform engineering education and improve the ethical impact of engineering practice.

1.2 Contribution and Significance

Extant theories of moral development (e.g., [4]) have limited application to engineering and to populations of diverse university students. In particular, existing theory tends to emphasize individuals’ decisions and actions without accounting for the environment in which those decisions are made or the sociocultural mediators of their agency, and this approach reflects microethics. Engineering practice, however, is increasingly recognising the importance of macroethics, the broader responsibilities of the engineering profession within organizational and societal contexts with respect to issues such as climate change, artificial intelligence, and social inequality [5]. Finelli et al. developed a conceptual framework of ethical development during university based on an input-environment-output model for studying students’ outcomes [6]. The framework posits that inputs (student characteristics) and the environment (inside and outside the classroom) inform students’ ethical development. Although the framework provides a helpful starting point for understanding the broad components that shape ethics education, it is conceptualised as quality (level of students’ involvement) and quantity (variety of experience and amount of time students invest) and has a microethical emphasis, as evidenced by how ethical development was measured in the student survey. Additionally, prior work aggregates engineering fields, but engineering is not monolithic with each discipline having a distinct culture, degree-specific outcomes, and relevant ethical issues [7]. As a result, it is instructive to disaggregate engineering to provide a more nuanced understanding of macroethical development. This study focuses on civil and architectural engineering due to its unique work at the nexus of the human and built environment.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Design

This research employs a constructivist grounded theory approach (CGT) [8] to address the research question: How do civil and architectural engineering students

develop their macroethical responsibility through their university experience? CGT is a qualitative systematic process for collecting and analysing data to generate new theory. The overarching perspective in this study is constructivism, which postulates that people construct knowledge based on their experiences. Instead of seeking an absolute truth, constructivism acknowledges that social and cultural factors mediate individuals' ability to make meaning of their experience and knowledge.

2.2 Data Collection

The study takes a cross-sectional approach to include participants at every level of their Bachelor's studies in civil and architectural engineering. The data collection and analysis occur in parallel until saturation is reached; around 30 individuals is common in CGT [9]. Participants are recruited via email invitations through the civil and architectural engineering programmes at one institution in the United Kingdom and one in Belgium. Intensive, semi-structured interviews [8] suitable to the need for flexibility to elicit the participants' authentic perspectives and co-construct meaning through their experience, lasting approximately an hour, will follow.

2.3 Data Analysis

The analysis follows the coding procedure of CGT [8]. The overarching process is the constant comparative method and is defined by initial and focused coding. Initial coding stays close to the data to develop emergent understandings of actions and processes within the transcripts. It takes an incident-by-incident approach in which the unit of analysis focuses on critical incidents that can be compared within the interview. Focused coding involves synthesizing and sharpening the initial codes based on what is most relevant and significant in the data. The resulting more conceptual codes will reflect tentative attempts toward theory building. Given the interplay between data collection and analysis, theoretical sampling will occur in parallel, using emerging theory to select participants to fill crucial holes in the data and refine ideas.

Sensitizing concepts serve as guideposts in grounded theory to draw attention to potentially important aspects of the phenomenon under investigation. **Agency**, conceptualized here as the "socioculturally mediated capacity to act" [10] (p. 112). Engineering ethics education is often framed as developing individual moral agency [11]. However, a narrow focus on individual agency neglects environmental factors that enable and hamper agency, and as a result, practicing engineers often perceive their agency is limited in the face of ethical dilemmas [12]. Ethics training of future engineers should reflect agency in the macroethical perspective. **Engagement** has an important role in learning and student achievement. Drawing on Lawson and Lawson's sociocultural framework [13], this research synthesizes engagement as a meta-construct with affective, cognitive, and behavioural components. This conceptualisation of engagement aligns with the affective, cognitive, and behavioural considerations in ethics while also integrating experiences inside and outside the classroom to reflect the multiple avenues through which students engage and develop an understanding of ethics. **Emotion** is inextricably connected to ethical

decision making and risk evaluation in engineering [14]. However, engineering ethics education gives limited attention to emotion [15].

3 EXPECTED OUTCOME

3.1 Next Steps

Interviews were conducted with eight architectural engineering students at one university in Belgium in May 2022. Data analysis is ongoing and preliminary findings indicate minimal, if any, framing of ethics in the curriculum but each student pointed to a course or a professor who integrated notions of responsibility and impact. Since engineering is ubiquitous in the world around us, student expressed a background awareness of these concepts, but it was not until they were formally discussed in the classroom that students began to contextualize and internalize them. One participant described a single mention of responsibility by a professor as a “domino effect” after which he began to see responsibility throughout his understanding of architectural engineering. Students also expressed feeling anxiety and pressure related to their future responsibilities given the impact of engineering on human lives and the built environment. Data collection will continue with students in the United Kingdom in September and October 2022.

3.2 Theoretical Model Development

This research will develop a theoretical model of civil and architectural engineering students’ macroethical development with the aim of addressing how agency and engagement can be fostered in the classroom and how informal outside of the classroom can be leveraged.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study is designed to explore civil and architectural engineering students’ conceptualisations of societal responsibility and the impact of engineering. The aim is to contribute a novel theoretical model of macroethical development with implications for engineering educators, administrators, and policymakers seeking to prepare students for the sociotechnical realities of engineering practice and the ethical expectations of the profession.

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